

Rethinking European Semiconductors: Open Architectures and Strategic IP

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Deliverable Abstract

This policy brief discusses how Intellectual Property (IP) management impacts innovation in the semiconductors industry. The brief analyses the growing role of hybrid models that combine protection and openness. Among these are cross-licensing agreements, patent pools and open architectures like RISC-V. The aim is to show how these models can promote collaboration, reduce barriers, and strengthen industrial resilience. In the European context, the brief highlights the need to harmonise IP practices, strengthen training and expertise, and take an active role in shaping open architectures and international standards, supporting the Union's technological sovereignty.

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Executive summary

Intellectual Property (IP) has long been a strategic pillar of the semiconductor industry, a key element in the research and design phases where technological advantage is defined. Over time, IP management has progressively transformed from a simple innovation protection tool to a competitive and geopolitical lever, in this interdependent industry characterised by rapid technological cycles. At the same time, global dynamics, from the diffusion of open architectures such as RISC-V to cross-licensing mechanisms and patent pools, demonstrate how hybrid models combining openness and protection can accelerate development, reduce access barriers, and strengthen industrial capacity. Europe benefits from advanced expertise and a multi-faceted protection system, founded on a dual framework between national instruments and European mechanisms, but needs to strengthen the capacity to exploit IP as a strategic asset, particularly for start-ups and SMEs that often struggle to fully value their securities and make them enforceable. In this context, the policy brief proposes an evolutionary path towards a more cooperative ecosystem, where IP allows not only to protect innovation, but also to share and multiply it. The main policy insights calls for harmonising legal instruments to foster greater clarity in open hardware licences, support European participation in open global standard setting and strengthen IP expertise throughout the supply chain, so as to consolidate a European model capable of integrating ownership and openness to strengthen the resilience and technological sovereignty of the Union.

1. Introduction: The critical role of IP in semiconductor R & D

In the semiconductor sector, Intellectual Property (IP) is a central element. Considering the breadth of technologies, products and industries directly related to this industry, IP in this area cannot be identified with a single form of protection, but is divided into different tools and assets that reflect the variety of applications and solutions that can be more or less sophisticated.

From a design perspective, IP is generally defined as a collection of pre-designed and pre-verified design components¹, such as processor cores, memory controllers, and interface protocols, that companies can reuse or licence. These readily available IP blocks are foundational for modern chip development because their integration offers strategic advantages: they significantly accelerate chip development, drastically reducing both time-to-market and design costs. However, In the semiconductor sector, Intellectual Property (IP) also encompasses patents, integrated circuit topographies, embedded software, trade secrets, and even trademarks, all of which together form the strategic knowledge base underpinning chip development. The coexistence of these diverse forms of IP, each with its own strategic function, underscores the inherent complexity of the semiconductor sector, demonstrating the challenge of effectively capturing chip innovation within a single, uniform IP framework, a challenge that will be explored in more detail in this session. This complexity is now amplified by the fact that this industry is currently experiencing dynamic growth, yet this demand is increasingly channelled by emerging sectors, most notably Artificial Intelligence (AI), which requires highly specialised and customised chips. This structural necessity is intensifying both the complexity of design and the pace of innovation, thereby making the strategic management of Intellectual Property (IP) a far more crucial factor than in markets with longer product lifecycles. Indeed, this short product life cycles, due to the rapid pace of technological innovation make it also difficult for companies to stay ahead and keep pace with the evolution of new technologies². It is therefore necessary to examine IP rights in the sector, considering that the creation of IP is also a high value-added activity in ICT production, whose economic impact is often underestimated.

At the same time, the role of IP is part of a context in which semiconductors have become a globally strategic technology, central to AI, security and industrial competitiveness. Furthermore, the sector can be exposed to a high risk of rapid imitation and reverse engineering. This growing relevance has progressively transformed IP from a simple innovation support and business enabler to a competitive and geopolitical lever, with an increase in portfolios and defensive practices. In this sector, characterised by cumulative innovation and strong interdependence, it is necessary to balance the need for protection to safeguard investments from value theft with the need for collaboration and standardisation imposed by the global chip supply chain. This explains why today the debate on openness and more flexible forms of technology sharing is becoming increasingly central. This policy brief places particular emphasis on new open approaches, cross-licensing agreements, and collaborative practices, with the aim of showing how IP can fuel innovation in increasingly open scenarios and in a sector where connectivity is playing a growing role, without compromising the importance and protection of rights.

Moreover, the research and innovation phase is particularly relevant for Europe. It is during this phase, specifically design, that the key functionalities of a chip are defined, along with its security features. This

1 Ikka T., (2009), The future of semiconductor intellectual property architectural blocks in Europe

2 Global Market Insight (2025) Dimensione del mercato della proprietà intellettuale (PI) dei semiconduttori - Per tipo di PI, fonte PI, core PI, analisi dell'uso finale, quota, previsioni di crescita, 2025-2034. <https://www.gminsights.com/it/industry-analysis/semiconductor-intellectual-property-ip-market>

explains why analysing the dynamics of intellectual property is of strategic importance for Europe, but also for the United States, which still maintains its comparative advantage in the upstream development phase. Without a solid position in these early stages, the other stages of the supply chain, particularly manufacturing, which is largely concentrated in Asia, would have limited strategic value. For this reason, discussing IP is essential not only as a legal protection measure, but also as a key to understanding the strategic role of the various players and the cumulative nature of technological innovation.

Considering the importance of management, sharing, and licensing, this policy brief focuses in particular on the interaction and enhancement of IP, reasoning above all in terms of intellectual capital and know-how. The main goal is to challenge the conventional view of IP as a mere barrier to absolute protection, demonstrating that the expansion of open innovation approaches is crucial. The brief addresses the strategic role of intellectual property, starting with the evolution in patent management and the geopolitical tensions that characterise the sector, and then analysing rights management and their impact on technological progress. It also provides a concise picture of the European IP landscape, highlighting regulatory developments and the tendency of many companies to prioritise protection at the national level, with reference to costs, complexities, and structural challenges for SMEs and start-ups. In this context, the brief explores the need for a more cooperative ecosystem, where open architectures and hybrid approaches demonstrate how traditional IP and openness can integrate to accelerate technological development. It also presents examples of how open architectures have been adopted internationally, including India and China.

1.1 PATENT EVOLUTION, LEGAL AMBIGUITIES IN INTEGRATED CIRCUIT LAYOUTS, AND THE GEOPOLITICAL DRIVERS OF PATENTING

The various stages of innovation and commercialisation in the sector have led to a natural evolution in intellectual property (IP) strategies. Innovation in semiconductors has manifested itself through extensive use of patents, a remarkable fact considering that, in principle, **integrated circuit (IC)** layouts were not considered fully eligible for traditional patent protection. This was because, in practice, layouts were often considered obvious variations of pre-existing designs, and it was difficult to describe them adequately in verbal form in a patent context, where the design itself has only an illustrative function³.

In the early days, this legal ambiguity, combined with corporate strategies and government policies, facilitated a spirit of disclosure and technology sharing. Patents served primarily as a tool for sharing among key players through broad cross-licensing agreements, while limiting litigation and promoting cumulative innovation. However, in the early 1980s, the landscape changed. Growing concern among US companies about being overtaken technologically by Japanese companies sparked accusations of IP infringement and highlighted the strategic role of semiconductors in global competition⁴. Since then, there has been a marked expansion in the use of patents for semiconductors, a phenomenon that has affected both the United States and the rest of the world. This shift transformed IP from a primary tool for sharing to a defensive and offensive barrier, highlighting the geopolitical relevance of this critical technology. Given the inherent complexity of semiconductors, chips do not always lend themselves to protection that can be perfectly framed in terms of patents. For this reason, there are various protection tools in this sector that integrate or complement the patents themselves. These include **trademarks**, which can be applied directly to the chip and can be visible under a microscope; **copyright**, which often takes the form of rights related exclusively to chip design. More specific tools such as *sui generis* rights for semiconductor

3 Hoeren T. et al (2015), Breakthrough Technologies, Semiconductor, Innovation and Intellectual Property, WIPO.

4 Zeng, Ka. (2004) Trade Threats, Trade Wars: Bargaining, Retaliation, and American Coercive Diplomacy. University of Michigan Press. <https://doi.org/10.3998/mpub.17690>. Chapter 5, U.S.–Japan Trade Conflicts: Semiconductors and Super 301 pp. 127-167.

topography, designed to protect the layout and internal architecture of integrated circuits⁵, with the original aim of prevent original microchip or integrated circuit designs from being copied and commercially exploited, whether in their original form or as components of other products⁶. In addition to these are **trade secrets**, as well as the protection of associated software, which plays a crucial role in embedded systems and advanced applications⁷. These mechanisms require strategic choices and compromises: for example, trade secrets do not expire like patents, but their validity is linked to the strict maintenance of specific confidentiality policies by the entity that holds them. Patents are ideal for inventions that are easily identifiable in the final products, while trade secrets are more suitable for improvements or internal processes that are difficult to detect externally⁸. Furthermore, the digital age, and especially the expansion of the internet, has increased the risk of trade secrets being stolen. This danger is amplified by the crucial role of semiconductors in emerging sectors such as artificial intelligence⁹.

1.2 INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY: MANAGEMENT, SHARING, AND IMPACT ON TECHNOLOGICAL PROGRESS

Once acquired, all these rights become a fundamental asset for companies. However, the real complexity emerges not so much in their individual existence, but rather when these rights are exchanged, transferred, and related to each other. For this reason it is important to focus on the concept of **licensing** and **transfer agreements**, around which the true strategic value of IP is realised: they shape who can access technology, influence market dynamics, and help cumulative innovation. In this sector, many advances are system-level innovations, building on previous knowledge rather than isolated breakthroughs. If IP is treated purely as a protective tool, without attention to its collaborative and cumulative potential, future innovation may be constrained rather than promoted. This is particularly true because semiconductor IP blocks are deeply integrated into these systems, giving IP regimes a decisive role in technological development patterns¹⁰. In other words, in this sector, IP strategy must transcend traditional protection to focus on tools functional to technological progress and innovation.

5 World Intellectual Property Organisation, Patent Expert Issues: Layout Designs (Topographies) of Integrated Circuits https://www.wipo.int/en/web/patents/topics/integrated_circuits

6 Directive 87/54/EEC on the legal protection of topographies of semiconductor products, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/1987/54/oj/eng>

7 In 2015, the World Semiconductor Council agreed on a series of fundamental elements in a model legislation regarding the protection of trade secrets and the explicit recognition of trade secrets as a form of intellectual property in accordance with Article 1.2 of the TRIPS, World semiconductor Council (2015), Excerpt from the joint statement of the 19 meeting of the WSC

8 Thompson A., Lubbock M. (2023) EU Chips Act: key intellectual Property considerations

9 World semiconductor Council (2021), Joint statement of the 25 meetings of the WSC

10 Ikka T., (2009), The future of semiconductor intellectual property architectural blocks in Europe, Marc Bogdanowicz.

2. Assessment of EU initiatives and current European mechanism

The global and coordinated nature of the semiconductor value chain makes analysis of the EU approach crucial. It is not just a question of understanding the legal instruments; it is essential to gauge Europe's ability to establish itself as a cohesive entity in a highly competitive and interdependent environment. The European intellectual property approach is defined by an inherently complex dual structure, where national protection systems coexist with centralised procedures offered by bodies like the **European Patent Office (EPO)** and the **EU Intellectual Property Office (EUIPO)**. Although this coexistence creates a complex system and takes time to navigate, it offers considerable strategic flexibility. Stakeholders, particularly SMEs and start-ups, can choose the option that best suits their budget and ambitions: pursuing broader protection at European level, more expensive and complex, or limiting themselves to national protection.

In general, the intellectual property system in Europe has always been highly fragmented, and little has changed at the legislative level over the past 20 years. However, the EU continues to work towards making patent protection more efficient, accessible and affordable for Member States. One example of this effort is the **EU Unitary Patent**, launched on 1 June 2023, which represents a quantum leap forward compared to the traditional EPO system: while maintaining the same standards for granting patents, it eliminates the need for costly and complex individual validation and renewal procedures in each country, offering uniform and centralised protection in 18, and potentially 25, Member States with a single application¹¹. Although the dual structure of the European IP system combining national offices with European-level mechanisms offers flexibility and theoretical opportunities, in practice most actors in the semiconductor sector tend to rely primarily on national patent filings rather than pursuing broader European protection, also among major industry players. Semiconductor companies often seek protection in Germany, directly with the German patent office. In fact, according to the EPO's 2024 patent index, Germany and France are the top two countries in Europe in terms of the number of patent applications¹². This is partly explained by the limited semiconductor manufacturing presence in Europe: absent a competitive domestic market, the strategic value of obtaining expensive, EU-wide protection is often perceived as low. This is because, despite the importance of innovation and efforts at European level, the costs of obtaining a unitary patent remain higher. In fact, although it reduces renewal costs, it remains complex for those who want only partial protection and not protection in all countries¹³.

Considering the high costs and complexity of the procedures, even the unitary patent, despite simplifying administrative management and reducing renewal costs compared to traditional nationalisation, does not solve all problems. For many companies, especially start-ups, the real issue is not accumulating patents, but being able to transform them into concrete, marketable technologies. In this context, it becomes clear that the challenge is not about who has the most patents, but who can translate them into market-ready technologies.

11 European Patent Office (2025), Unitary Patent & Unified Patent Court <https://www.epo.org/en/applying/european/unitary>

12 European Patent Office (2025), Patent Index 2024: European innovation remains robust amid global economic uncertainties

13 Select Committee of the Administrative Council of the European Patent Organisation. Rules relating to Unitary Patent Protection as adopted by decision of the Select Committee of the Administrative Council of 15 December 2015 and last amended by decision of 23 March 2022, implementing Regulation (EU) No 1257/2012 and Council Regulation (EU) No 1260/2012 on unitary patent protection and translation arrangements. European Patent Organisation.

2.1 STRUCTURAL DISADVANTAGES: IMPACT OF COSTS AND COMPLEXITY ON SMES AND STARTUPS

An issue that emerged from the interviews concerns the behaviour of start-ups, which are often the most fragile but also the most innovative players in the ecosystem. The crucial point is not so much obtaining the patent as its actual use. Some interviewees pointed out that, in most cases, start-ups do not have a strategy to exploit the patents they file. The question that emerges most strongly is in fact more subtle: once the title has been acquired, is there a concrete strategy for exploiting it, for example, through licences, collaborations or technology transfer, or does it remain an inactive asset? According to some interviewees, many young companies tend to view patents primarily as a formal requirement: something to be obtained in order to satisfy investors' demands or to increase their valuation in view of a potential acquisition or Initial Public Offering (IPO). However, once obtained, patents often remain unused. This often leads to a paradoxical situation, where limited resources are spent on obtaining a title that sometimes ends up being dormant. Furthermore, considering the limited funds available for start-ups, spending a large part of them on the patenting process could also reduce the resources available to improve the product itself.

Furthermore, effective IP management represents a second, structural problem that distinguishes large players from SMEs and start-ups. Intellectual property (IP) users require suppliers to be reliable and consistent in managing rights during the entire product lifecycle. This comprehensive management typically requires a significant investment of resources, which is often prohibitive for smaller companies¹⁴. As a result, large providers enjoy a clear competitive advantage, as they can offer the coverage and depth of portfolio required by the market. To mitigate the complexity and inefficiency of legal licence negotiation processes, many large semiconductor companies have focused their strategies on building extensive patent portfolios especially to reinforce their position with competitors¹⁵. These extensive portfolios are used strategically: not only to protect investments and establish operational limits, but also to create room for negotiation through cross-licensing agreements. A historical example is represented by players such as **Texas Instruments** that have exploited their IP primarily for internal production and to constrain competitors, rather than for extensive licensing to external developers¹⁶. In summary, analysis of start-up cases and the strategies of major players in the semiconductor sector reveals a key principle for Europe: innovation is not measured only by the volume of patents. Many start-ups tie up limited resources in unused titles, while corporations exploit massive portfolios primarily for negotiation and protection, rather than as catalysts for real innovation. Especially considering the fast changing market demands that drive this sector, innovation, and differentiation are needed more than mere protection. A striking example comes from **Schneider Electric**, a global company in the industrial and energy sector. Historically, the company holds tens of thousands of patents covering even basic technologies, such as "switching on a switch". Although these patents represented sophisticated innovations in the past, many now protect incremental or widely available features, providing little added value to current products. Experts point out that if these companies reviewed their portfolios with a focus on what supports actual differentiation, they could eliminate up to 40% of the costs of filing and maintaining unnecessary patents.

This context provides the necessary premise for the subsequent discussion, which will focus on the importance of establishing support frameworks where innovation takes priority and can adequately meet market demands. The current discussion is framed by the understanding that chips will require increasingly specialised and customised characteristics.

14 Ikka T., (2009), The future of semiconductor intellectual property architectural blocks in Europe, Marc Bogdanowicz.

15 Comino, S., Manenti, F.M. Patent portfolios and firms' technological choices. J Econ 137, 97–120 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00712-022-00783-x>

16 Ikka T., (2009), The future of semiconductor intellectual property architectural blocks in Europe, Marc Bogdanowicz.

3. Global Dynamics: IP exposure and the open innovation response

The strategic use of patents and the creation of vast portfolios have historically defined the semiconductor industry, particularly for large players who exploited cross-licensing and internal protection to gain competitive advantages. However, as interviews revealed, the landscape is changing: today, the challenge is no longer simply the ownership of intellectual property, but the effective management and sharing of know-how and intellectual capital.

This strategic shift is part of the context of new open architectures focused on the external transfer of knowledge. In this context, the concept of **Outbound Open Innovation (OI)** helps to better understand the dynamics of technology flows moving from within an organisation to the outside, often through the granting of patent licences¹⁷. In this scenario, it should be noted that the relationship between IP protection and open innovation has often been considered complex and sometimes paradoxical, as protection mechanisms can act both as catalysts and enablers of technological diffusion and as obstacles to full openness, creating a sort of tension between knowledge sharing and protection in R&D collaborations¹⁸. The current debate on IP is often framed as a conflict between the protection of rights and the principles of openness. However, it would be more strategically useful to consider the open approach not as an antagonist to proprietary IP, but as an additional lever for development, enhancement and innovation in this interconnected sector. If open source is considered not primarily as a technology, but through the lens of a social movement aimed at promoting the sharing of know-how and collaboration, its evolution in the semiconductor sector shows how open foundations can support differentiated industrial strategies. The growing strategic importance of openness has also been recognised at EU level: the preliminary opinion of the **JURI Committee on the Chips Act** explicitly emphasises how open-source IP and free licensing can become a fundamental pillar for a competitive European semiconductor ecosystem¹⁹. The importance of these considerations is heightened when taking into account that 2026 will be a strategic year for the EU and the sector. With the evolution of the **Chips Act 2.0**, certain strategic priorities will undoubtedly be the adoption of faster and more flexible instruments for expansion and scale up and support for European force sectors. Such areas specifically include AI, Edge AI, and microcontrollers for robotics, making thinking about the optimal implementation of innovation even more urgent to maintain competitive advantage and technological sovereignty.

3.1 RISC - V AN EXAMPLE OF STRATEGIC OPPORTUNITY

Various tools and organisational models already demonstrate how openness can coexist with IP regimes. Among these, **RISC-V** is a particularly illustrative example: contrary to certain political concerns, such as those expressed by some US policymakers regarding a possible threat to national security and competitive advantage²⁰, the openness of RISC-V does not expose sensitive information or require companies to disclose their proprietary IP. In fact, companies do not compete on the open standard itself, but on the

17 Linus Dahlander, David M. Gann, How open is innovation? (2010) *Research Policy*, Volume 39, Issue 6, Pages 699-709.

18 Bogers, Marcel. (2010). The Open Innovation Paradox: Knowledge Sharing and Protection in R&D Collaborations. *European Journal of Innovation Management*. 14. 10.1108/14601061111104715

19 European Parliament, Committee on Legal Affairs (JURI), Draft Opinion for the Committee on Industry, Research and Energy on the proposal for a regulation establishing a framework of measures for strengthening Europe's semiconductor ecosystem (Chips Act), 4 October 2022, Rapporteur: Tiemo Wölken (COM(2022)0046 – C9-0039/2022 – 2022/0032(COD)).

20 Shivakumar, S., & Heng, J. (2025). Sustaining Standards Leadership: The United States Cannot Disengage from RISC-V. CSIS, Center for Strategic and International Studies.

differentiated technologies they build on top of it. This makes **RISC-V** a flexible, low-risk, low-cost platform that advance collaboration without compromising protection²¹. In 2025, **RISC-V** obtained **ISO/IEC JTC1** accreditation, allowing **RISC-V** to be recognised as a **Standards Development Organisation (SDO)** and making its specifications eligible for the accelerated procedure to become **ISO standards**²². Furthermore, precisely because of the nature of openness, nothing prevents companies from developing proprietary extensions on **ISA RISC-V**: the architecture offers a shared basis, but leaves complete freedom to build exclusive modules and maintain control over their own additions. A concrete example is the Chinese **Alibaba T-Head**, which has developed the **RISC-V XuanTie** core line.²³ It is a high-performance processor compatible with the RISC-V architecture, which, according to the manufacturer, achieves industry-leading computational performance and frequencies thanks to innovations in architecture and microarchitecture but is nonetheless configured as a brand under the aegis of Alibaba DAMO Academy, further confirming its internal strategic importance²⁴. It is also worth noting that **NVIDIA**, the US company that today boasts the most important proprietary **GPUs** for artificial intelligence, which have had a disruptive influence on the market,²⁵ has been employing **RISC-V** for years internally in its **GPUs** as the Falcon controller²⁶. In 2024, based on the total number of chips shipped, the company surpassed the milestone of 1 billion integrated RISC-V processors²⁷. **RISC-V** has also been central to the Indian government's strategy, which, through the **DIR-V programme**, launched by the Ministry of Electronics & IT, aims to develop indigenous microprocessors based on **RISC-V**, with regional extensions, without compromising the original openness and considering **RISC -V** as the Indian national ISA. This commitment is an integral part of a broader strategy of technological self-sufficiency in the sector: the objective is supported by concrete projects for indigenous microprocessors such as the **RISCV Microprocessor Shakti**²⁸ and **VEGA microprocessor**²⁹.

The scale of this innovation and widespread adoption, illustrated by the specific case studies **Alibaba**, **NVIDIA** and India, underscores the strategic value of **RISC-V**. For decades, in fact, instruction architectures have been controlled by a few private companies, such as AMD, ARM and Intel, owners of the most common processor architectures³⁰. This level of control led to a slow evolution of these proprietary **ISAs**, failing to keep pace with new application needs. The strength of **RISC V** lies instead in its modular and extensible design, which ensures compatibility with previous versions, while allowing research efforts to take place at the community level, distributing costs and risks³¹. This challenge has led controllers of proprietary **ISAs** to increase the speed of their development efforts.

21 Shivakumar, S., & Heng, J. (2025). Sustaining Standards Leadership: The United States Cannot Disengage from RISC-V. CSIS, Center for Strategic and International Studies.

22 Gallo, A. (2025, 21 ottobre). *RISC-V Takes First Step Toward International Standardization as ISO/IEC JTC1 Grants PAS Submitter Status*. RISC-V International. <https://riscv.org/blog/risc-v-jtcl-pas-submitter/>

23 L. Zhang et al., "Xuantie-910: A Commercial Multi-Core 12-Stage Pipeline Out-of-Order 64-bit High Performance RISC-V Processor with Vector Extension," in Proc. 2020 ACM/IEEE 47th Annual Int. Symp. on Computer Architecture (ISCA), 2020

24 XuanTie. https://www.xrvm.com/overview/about_us

25 Wang, John & Hsu, Jeffrey & Qin, Zhaoqiong. (2024). A Comprehensive Analysis of Nvidia's Technological Innovations, Market Strategies, and Future Prospects. International Journal of Information Technologies and Systems Approach. 17. 1-16. 10.4018/IJITSA.344423.

26 L. Zhang et al., "Xuantie-910: A Commercial Multi-Core 12-Stage Pipeline Out-of-Order 64-bit High Performance RISC-V Processor with Vector Extension," in Proc. 2020 ACM/IEEE 47th Annual Int. Symp. on Computer Architecture (ISCA), 2020

27 F. Sijstermans et al., "RISC-V at NVIDIA: One Architecture, Dozens of Applications, Billions of Processors," keynote, RISC-V Summit, 2024.

28 Kamakoti, V., et al. *SHAKTI – An Indigenous RISC-V Microprocessor from Bharat. (2021)*. Prathap Subrahmanyam Centre for Digital Intelligence and Secure Hardware Architecture, IIT Madras. <https://amritmahotsav.negd.in/presentation/day5/SHAKTI%20%E2%80%93%20An%20Indigenous%20RISCV%20Microprocessor%20from%20Bharat.pdf>

29 Centre for Development of Advanced Computing (C-DAC). (2025). DIR-V Program – C-DAC continuous contributions in High-Performance VEGA Microprocessors.

30 Gupta, Khushi & Sharma, Tushar. (2021). Changing Trends in Computer Architecture : A Comprehensive Analysis of ARM and x86 Processors. International Journal of Scientific Research in Computer Science, Engineering and Information Technology. 619-631. 10.32628/CSEIT2173188.

31 Open Source Hardware & Software Working Group. (2022). Recommendations and roadmap for European sovereignty in open source hardware, software, and RISC-V technologies.

For Europe, this open source approach can be considered as a potential instrument of sovereignty, offering an alternative to non-EU IP and drastically lower the barriers to designing innovative **System-On-Chips (SoCs)**, an area in which Europe excels³². The goal is not only research and development in the sector, but the creation of a critical mass of trusted European core IP, which can be crucial for critical sectors such as automotive and defence.

3.2 HYBRID GOVERNANCE AND IP INTEGRATION: THE CROSS-LICENCES APPROACH AND THE ROLE OF PATENT MANAGEMENT

The adoption of open tools such as **RISC-V** demonstrates that technological innovation in semiconductors is evolving and can demonstrate that also a hybrid approach and coexistence with proprietary IP is possible. A significant example is the **Open Invention Network (OIN)**, created by long-standing players such as **IBM, Sony, and Philips**³³ to neutralise the negative effect of large patent trolls.

Its operation as a strategic patent pool provides protection from patent litigation, as membership commits members not to sue other participants, access to a large pool of cross-licences, and the ability to build on others' ideas without legal obstacles, in a community which owns over 3 million patents and applications in total³⁴. The fact that most of the world's major patent holders are part of this community, demonstrates how intellectual property can be integrated into a strategic model where innovation and collaboration are priorities. For a start-up that, for example, owns only one patent, or a limited number of patents, free membership of **OIN** grants access to millions of patents in the pool that can be used for defence against potential litigation. This can be an advantage especially in a scenario where usually, the company size gives large enterprises considerable negotiating power, allowing them to define the conditions that smaller players are often forced to accept³⁵. It is also a fact that patent disputes, often abusive, are common practice and can seriously undermine innovation. This is mainly because they divert research expenditure and other resources towards unnecessary legal costs or engineering around an existing patent, also making it more difficult to launch products on the market³⁶. A good best practice, reflecting this approach is indeed, in Europe, **OVH Cloud**, a European leader in cloud service delivery, in 2020, joined **OIN** with an initiative involving the company to conduct a detailed review of its open source software usage, mapping it against **OIN**'s existing protections³⁷. The process resulted in the inclusion of several hundred software packages within the cross-licensing commitment.

As highlighted by industry experts, such cross-licensing agreements embody the concept of **co-opetition**: cooperating at a low level (low-stack) in order to compete more effectively at a higher, differentiated level (high-stack). This practice does not imply abandoning patents: members actively maintain their proprietary IP, being able to choose where to share and where to maintain control. The essence of commercial success lies precisely in this strategic combination between open and owner. The fundamental goal, therefore, should be to preserve freedom of technological choice and innovation, preventing patents from becoming a tool to hinder the evolution of innovation.

32 Open Source Hardware & Software Working Group. (2022.) Recommendations and roadmap for European sovereignty in open source hardware, software, and RISC-V technologies.

33 Open Invention Network, Funding Members and Licenses <https://www.openinventionnetwork.com/our-members/funding-members-and-licensees/>

34 Open Invention Network, OIN's portfolio consists of 12 global patents and applications.

35 Sime Tchouaso, S., Hagedoorn, J. & Tan, H. Power dynamics and outbound openness: licensing exclusivity choices in the semiconductor industry. J Technol Transf (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10961-025-10259-x>

36 World Semiconductor Council. (2019). Joint statement of the 23rd meeting of the World Semiconductor Council (WSC), Xiamen, China.

37 OVHcloud. (2020). OVHcloud joins Open Invention Network and renews its commitment to Open Source. Press release.

3.3 GLOBAL BENCHMARKING: IP EXPOSURE IN THE US AND THE EXAMPLE OF CHINA

The debate over IP management and the adoption of open models cannot ignore its global strategic relevance, considering the actual scenario where much of the IP for semiconductor design remains in US hands³⁸, effectively creating technological dependence for many countries. This supremacy is amplified by US control over the crucial **Electronic Design Automation tools (EDA)**, necessary for hardware design, from logic synthesis to backend implementation, which act as the main technological control point. Despite the excellence of European research in this field, the system is held back by the acquisition of European startups by US-controlled companies³⁹.

In this context, the use of an effective strategy becomes crucial, even considering that the costs associated with patent registration and management in some European regions continue to significantly exceed those in the United States and China. As broadly pointed out by interviewees, China's technology ecosystem, while maintaining a hybrid approach, is actively supporting the development of open source and **RISC-V** technologies, with strong support from both the central and regional authorities. China seeks to exploit the potential of open source while always remaining in a geopolitical dynamic in which it seeks to reduce dependence on external IP. As previously mentioned in this brief, a case in point is clearly demonstrated by the **Xuantie** processor family (C920, C907, R910), launched by the research division of the Chinese Company **Alibaba**. This can be considered a strategic attempt by the People's Republic of China to "escape US led technological containment"⁴⁰ by leveraging open source hardware.

This push is not just industrial: the government and major Chinese universities, such as **Tsinghua University**, widely use **RISC-V** for student training in chip engineering and for research in advanced fields such as Artificial Intelligence⁴¹. Through its **Shenzhen headquarters Tsinghua Shenzhen International Graduate School (SIGS)**, inaugurated a laboratory dedicated to **RISC-V**: the **RISC-V International Open Source Laboratory (RIOS Lab)**, that is designed for research and training in **RISC-V** hardware and software. A further tangible example of this ecosystem is provided by **Espressif Systems**⁴². **Espressif** is a Shanghai-based company that produces low-cost devices, which are also available for as little as one dollar, equipped with **RISC-V CPUs**. These devices, which handle Wi-Fi and Bluetooth, are widely used for **IoT** and embedded applications, and much of their work is returned to the open source community. This case demonstrates that investing in **RISC-V** can translate into high-volume products that benefit from the collaborative approach. For many experts, the onerous nature of traditional IP systems is one reason why open architectures like **RISC-V** are finding rapid adoption in China, as in other emerging contexts, they reduce entry costs for innovation, eliminate the need for complex and limit exposure to legal risks, typical of more fragmented software and hardware segments. Considering the growing influence of Chinese entities in the **RISC-V International Foundation** a clear indicator of China's intention to guide the development of **RISC-V** and redefine the global technological order by shifting control from the United States⁴³, confirms

38 World Intellectual Property Indicators (2024): Patents Highlights. <https://www.wipo.int/web-publications/world-intellectual-property-indicators-2024-highlights/en/patents-highlights.html#:~:text=The%20US%20has%20held%20top,fold%20growth%20in%20abroad%20filings>

39 Open Source Hardware & Software Working Group. (2022.) Recommendations and roadmap for European sovereignty in open source hardware, software, and RISC-V technologies.

40 Cheung, S. (2023). Examining China's Grand Strategy for RISC-V: Civil-Military Fusion. China Brief, (23).

41 Tsinghua Shenzhen International Graduate School. (2020). First China RISC-V Forum held at Tsinghua SIGS, A.M. Turing Award RIOS Laboratory unveiled. Tsinghua University.

42 Espressif Systems. (2020). Introducing ESP32-C3, a cost-effective, RISC-V-based MCU with Wi-Fi and Bluetooth 5 (LE) connectivity for secure IoT applications. Espressif Systems.

43 Cheung, S. (2023). Examining China's Grand Strategy for RISC-V: Civil-Military Fusion. China Brief, (23).

how, regardless of geopolitical motivations, the real challenge lies in keeping up with the strategic evolution of intellectual property models. In this scenario, it becomes essential to understand that openness not only does not compromise competitiveness, but is its main driver in the actual evolving global scenario.

4. Policy Priorities

The semiconductor sector is a cornerstone of European technological sovereignty and innovation. The analysis highlighted how the current reliance on a few non-EU proprietary architectures and the fragmentation of the intellectual property (IP) regulatory framework constitute a significant brake on progress. The following policy recommendations are based on the strategic need to promote a hybrid and cooperative IP model in Europe, inspired by the principle of co-opetition and the adoption of open standards. The goal is twofold: harmonise EU IP practices to make them suitable for the open ecosystem, enhance legal clarity and predictability for SMEs and research communities and actively encourage the strategic shift towards open architecture, and shaping them, as tools of technological sovereignty, reducing entry costs and legal barriers to innovation.

4.1 RETHINKING EU IP PRACTICES: HARMONISATION OF THE LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR OPEN IP

Europe already has a set of valid legal tools for managing open intellectual property, including the EURL license for public sector software and several mechanisms for managing patents in collaborative contexts, such as non-subpoena pledges and legal declarations. However, the potential of these instruments is limited by their significant fragmentation and the lack of a universal licensing standard recognised in all 27 Member States. As pointed out by some of the experts interviewed, Europe has frameworks for software, but not a general licensing model that covers everything. In a crucial sector like semiconductors, the excessive variety of hardware licences and the difficulty of reconciling patents with copyleft obligations are blocking the development of a cohesive open ecosystem. Areas that could be considered as a strategic focus include:

- ③ **Standardisation and Uniformity:** Propose a Unified European licence and develop a generalised open licence model recognised in all Member States, overcoming the lack of a common standard that limits the effectiveness of existing models. This measure would not only reduce fragmentation and legal uncertainty, but would actually strengthen the functioning of the Single European Market. Companies could thus operate without friction across borders, participating in an open and coherent ecosystem.
- ③ **Define Models for Semiconductors:** Propose new hardware and chip-specific licensing models that take technical needs into account and clearly define how to integrate patent rights with open sharing requirements. These models need to provide predictable, long-term participation in open ecosystems, supporting interoperability while lowering barriers for SMEs and research communities. This approach is key to ensuring the European semiconductor sector can innovate collaboratively and maintain resilience against market and geopolitical instability.

4.2 STRATEGIC DEVELOPMENT: TRAINING, ECOSYSTEM AND ADOPTION OF OPEN ARCHITECTURES

The imperative of reducing dependence and strengthening European sovereignty requires an action plan that exploits the benefits of modularity and collaboration. Actually, Artificial Intelligence is redefining hardware requirements, with chips increasingly subservient to software. In this context, it is crucial to address the knowledge gap regarding the **reality and functioning of Intellectual Property (IP)**, a factor that, as found in interviews, hinders its strategic use. To ensure conscious and fundamental innovation, the strategic intervention must therefore start from the very foundation of **education and training**, integrating IP and innovation right from the earliest stages of instruction.

- ④ **Shaping Open Architectures at the European and International Level:** To fully exploit the strategic potential of open technologies and architectures, Europe should become a central player in the governance and development of these standards. Active engagement in international forums and consortia, such as **RISC-V International**, is essential to ensure that the evolution of open platforms is aligned with European industrial priorities and objectives. This active role, which complements training and ecosystem-building efforts, allows Europe not only to use open technologies, but to shape them according to its long-term strategic interests.
- ④ **Encourage Open Education:** Significantly fund open source hardware education at undergraduate and pre-college levels. By exploiting the tendency for European talent to remain in Europe, a critical mass of developers can be created and knowledge can be ensured to be shared and accessible in the long term. As also stated in this brief, this approach has been widely adopted by contexts such as China and India, which have integrated **RISC-V** into national strategies and educational programs to accelerate innovation. As experts have pointed out, open source has the potential to democratise chip design, making it accessible even to young students, with the possibility that “a 13-year-old approaching it” could actively participate in hardware design.
- ④ **Priority and Coordination (Roadmap case study):** Support coordinated actions at European level, following the model of the **Open Source Hardware and Software Roadmap for Europe** developed by the Open Source Hardware & Software Working Groups, to avoid fragmentation and create a critical mass of activities that expands the influence of the European open-source community on the global scenario, involving Universities, Research centers and Public institutions.

5. Conclusions

The semiconductor industry is among the most innovative and rapidly evolving sectors and it directly contributes to forming the layer of all modern technological infrastructure. To support technological progress and stimulate innovation in this context, it is necessary to transcend traditional models of intellectual property protection. This policy brief aimed to highlight how today simply owning intellectual property is not enough to guarantee competitive advantages: it is necessary to identify strategies and models capable of supporting innovation and knowledge sharing. Innovation ecosystems, particularly small businesses and emerging players, can benefit from complementary approaches such as open architectures, collaborative licensing, and hybrid models, which support innovation while accelerating technological progress, reducing barriers to entry, and supporting industrial resilience and strategic sovereignty, without reducing the value of intellectual property, but making it more strategic.

This analysis highlighted that open architectures such as RISC-V can offer a flexible, more accessible and low-risk model. Concrete examples notably NVIDIA's internal use of RISC-V and national initiatives exemplified by India's DIR-V programme illustrate how this strategy can support collaboration and stimulate the development of innovative processes. Similarly, cross-licensing networks such as the Open Invention Network provide a valid example of the benefits of a collaborative model that does not involve relinquishing control over proprietary assets. These tools, and global examples such as China, emphasise that adopting a more open approach, or mixed strategies between openness and protection, can make intellectual property more strategic and functional for the development of this crucial sector.

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